

SUMMARY AND PLAGIARISM PREVENTION.

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Abstract: This thesis discusses how to prevent plagiarism in various discourses, such as in academic writing, general writing and others, following summarizing in an appropriate and relevant way. There are briefly revealed types of plagiarism too.

Key words: summary, plagiarism, discourse, citation, quotation, author, essay, text, copy, avoid.

Summary is a short information about the whole discourse includes main points. It consists of brief information about what you read and understand. It should not be contained each details deeply. You do not need to indicate all details, just show main items that are found more important (Hunter college). Usually summary comes at the end of the discourse. Summary is required to be written with your own words without plagiarism. During your academic performance if you use any type of plagiarism, your work will be equaled to zero. Therefore always follow citing materials with author's name. In order not to use plagiarism you should enrich the range of your academic vocabulary. According to the type of your discourse you should collect main meaning in a particular. For example, if you write an essay or a text your summary should be reflected in three or four sentences. If it is a research article or a book, in that case the amount of summary is also expanded. As Clarkson and Natalia (2015) stated that summary is written in one paragraph, however the number of paragraphs are extended as from the work size.

Plagiarism is copying out one's work directly or with some changes like paraphrasing, rewording, changing sentence order and so on without citation or without the name of author. As it is stated in Webster Academic Integrity that plagiarism is considered as academic dishonesty and it is expressed deliberately and accidentally. There are ten types of plagiarism in Academic English. You should identify, differ and avoid using any of them. Following I briefly introduce you with the types of plagiarism:

1. **Clone.** This type of plagiarism is copying out another person's work directly word for word. Lack of time management or other academic poorness cause to this kind of plagiarism.

2. **CTRL-C.** In this type of plagiarism most parts of a text are stayed unchanged, students may add some linking words in some portions.

3. **Find-Replace.** It is reflected exchanging some words, key words, points in the text into synonym one. But the main meaning is kept.
4. **Remix.** It is clear from its name also that it is mixed view of different sources. In this method students get information about one topic from different sources and collect them in one place as it is their own work.
5. **Recycle.** In order to save their time or not having intention to create a new one, students reuse their previous work. Though it is their own work, own idea if the instructor does not allow, they cannot use their previous work in a new term again.
6. **Hybrid.** In this method of plagiarism, students make their work combining cited sources with copied portion.
7. **Mashup.** Like to CTRL-C and Remix type students mix plagiarized materials from diverse sources.
8. **404 Error.** As students' carelessness and confusion, they make this mistake. Here they express citation with irrelevant author.
9. **Aggregator.** It is the use of proper citation but the work of students is not considered as original work. because there is very little or no students' voice and addition.
10. **Re-Tweet.** This type of plagiarism is similar to Find-Replace one that students to change some key words and use synonym words to replace.

Below you can see some examples for CTRL-C and Find-Replace plagiarism and original summary of a student that is written without plagiarism.

During your academic performance if you use any type of plagiarism, your work will be equaled to zero. In order not to use plagiarism you should enrich the range of your academic vocabulary. According to the type of your discourse you should collect main meaning in a particular way. For example, if you write an essay, your summary should be reflected in two or three sentences. If it is a research article or a book, in that case the amount of summary is also expanded.

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